

X-ray diffraction and Optical studies of ZrO₂ Thin films prepared by Spray Pyrolysis Method

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Abstract

Thin film of zirconium oxide on glass substrate was prepared by spray pyrolysis method. Film thickness is determined by viewing cross section image from Scanning Electron Microscope. It is found to be 1.051 micron for the film prepared at 250°C. X-ray diffraction pattern indicate the material is of crystalline in nature with preferential orientation along (1 1 1) plane having grain size of 18 nm. Optical transmittance is studied using spectrophotometer in the wavelength range 380 - 800 nm. Optical transmittance curve shows a linear increase towards higher wavelength region and indicating crystalline nature of the film. Also optical transmittance has 85% in the higher wavelength region. Energy band gap of the film is obtained by plotting graph $h\nu$ Vs $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ and is found to be 2.57eV indicating semiconductor nature. The results thus obtained will be discussed in detail.

Keywords: Spray Pyrolysis, Energy band gap, Thin film, X-ray diffraction.

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